

THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE CHRISTIAN RELIGIOUS EDUCATION CURRICULUM OF EVANGELISM EXPLOSION INTERNATIONAL METHOD ON CHURCH CITIZENS AND CHURCH GROWTH IN SUMATRA, THE NORTH OF INDONESIA

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the level of the tendency of implementation of the theology of mission of Evangelism Explosion International's personal evangelism method, correlation/indicators of the theology of mission of Evangelism Explosion International's evangelism method and the contribution of the theology of mission of Evangelism Explosion International's evangelism method to the implementation of evangelism in the Indonesian Evangelical Presbyterian Church, North Sumatra Region. This research is an exploratory-confirmatory survey. The population in this study is everyone who has attended Evangelism Explosion training and people who have been served by using the Evangelism Explosion method in GPII Sumbagut Region. At the same time, the sample taken was 100 people from all EEI training participants. At the same time, the data collection tool used is a questionnaire that has been tested for validity and reliability. Path analysis (Path-Analysis) with regression principles is the data analysis technique. The results showed that the tendency to implement the theology of the mission of Evangelism Explosion International's evangelism method could be better. However, there are indications to increase in a higher direction. The Friendship indicator is closely related to the Gospel indicator and the Surrender indicator. However, it is not related to the Follow-up indicator. The Gospel indicator is closely related to the Surrender and Follow-Up indicators. At the same time, the Surrender indicator is not related to the Follow-up indicator. The most significant contribution to implementing the EEI personal evangelism method in the Sumbagut region of GPII is the Gospel indicator, which is indicated by a path coefficient of 0.911 and followed by the Friendship, Surrender and Follow-Up indicators.

Keywords: Curriculum, Christian Religious Education, Church Citizens, Church Growth, North Sumatra.

INTRODUCTION

The Church of God faces many unbiblical theologies, especially evangelism theology. Jacob B Susabda said that, If in the 16th century, the Reformers faced the challenge of reforming a spiritually and physically corrupt church, today's Evangelicals face slightly different challenges, namely: the challenge of evangelism in the modern age, the challenge of education theology the laity, the challenge of witnessing in a pluralistic world and the challenge to restore the authority of the Bible in preaching, witnessing, ministry and church life.

Then Stephen Tong fiercely challenged unevangelical theologies; in this case, many parties may disagree with me. Indeed, I fought alone to emphasize the importance of balancing theology and evangelism. However, I believe God commanded me to make the churches in Indonesia aware today that theology without evangelism is dead, and evangelism without theology is weak (Zega, 2021).

The role of evangelical theology is urgently needed in Indonesia's implementation of evangelism (Kusmanto, 2022). Chris Marantika argues that evangelical theology is the only feature theology that can meet the target theology of Indonesia and is purely Biblical. The Great Commission of Jesus Christ teaches believers to preach the Gospel of Salvation worldwide (Arifianto et al., 2020). This Great Commission is found in the four Gospels and in Rick Warren's Book of Acts gives views on the importance of the mission of believers; fulfilling your life mission in the world is an essential part of living for the glory of God (Surita, 2019). The Bible gives several reasons why your mission is so important. Your mission is a continuation of Jesus' mission in the world. As His followers, we must continue what Jesus started. Jesus calls us not only to come to Him but also to go to Him. Your mission is so essential that Jesus repeated it five times, in five different ways, in five different books of the Bible (Gultom, 2021). If all of God's people consistently and faithfully carry out the Great Commission, the church must grow (Silitonga, 2018). However, in reality, many believers still need to do this task. They do not want to know how vital evangelism is, and even many pastors are satisfied with their ministry as shepherds. William Barclay said that the Christian's duty now, as in other times, is to communicate The Gospel to everyone (Tarigan, 2021).

The problem is that many churches die yearly because they do not evangelize. In preaching the Gospel to others, a suitable method is essential. Because when communicating the Gospel to someone with inappropriate methods, those who are served will likely reject Jesus as their Lord and Savior. Because in evangelism, sometimes the essence of the Gospel message is already clearly conveyed, but if the approach or method is not correct, it can result in the rejection of the Gospel of Jesus by the person being evangelized (Mawakere & Hura, 2022). Incommunicate Gospel news and delivery methods are highly interconnected (Pasasa, 2016). This means that the process from approach to the delivery of the Gospel and also up to the challenge must support each other. Thus the appropriate method is an urgent need in evangelism. Moreover, a lay evangelist needs the correct method. Researchers believe that only some effective methods can be used in all conditions or places in carrying out evangelism. Researchers have indeed experienced this in carrying out the task of evangelism. Because of that, there are many methods of evangelism. There are many ways of preaching the Gospel, for example, in bulk, in person, radio, TV, music, drama, and tracts. One emerging personal evangelism method is the Evangelism Explosion International (EEI) method designed by James Kennedy in the United States Presbyterian Church.

In Medan in 2001, a representative for Evangelism Explosion International was opened. The management of EE Medan has struggled to equip believers individually and as a group in personal evangelism. Many churches, campuses and Christian foundations have participated in the Evangelism Explosion training, including the Indonesian Evangelical Presbyterian Church in the northern Sumatra region that has implemented it. Because of that, the researcher wants to examine the implementation of the Evangelism Explosion method in the Indonesian Evangelical Presbyterian Church in the Northern Sumatra Region so that it is poured into writing the dissertation. Orientation evangelists have undergone many changes, but these changes do not seem to indicate progress towards the more professionalism-oriented approaches to the Bible. Based on the observations of researchers in the field and also by paying attention to sources from books that have been published, there are indications that, on the one hand, evangelization in Indonesia is only carried out by certain circles.

Then many of the methods are oriented from the West; of course, in a Western context, it is not confident that they will be successfully implemented in Indonesia. Based on the description of the background of the problem, the researcher is interested in conducting research titled "The Implementation Of The Christian Religious Education Curriculum Of Evangelism Explosion International Method On Church Citizens And Church Growth In Sumatra, The North Of Indonesia."

LITERATURE REVIEW

Evangelism Explosion

Evangelism Explosion, abbreviated as EE International, is a method of personal evangelism. Method Evangelism Explosion International is not only one method of personal evangelism but one of many methods of personal evangelism. With the Evangelism Explosion method, there is expected to be a tremendous explosion of evangelism (Singgih, 2020). This method equips churches for success in friendship, evangelism, discipleship and healthy church growth. Evangelism Explosion has a systematic curriculum so that evangelized people want to accept Christ personally as their Lord and Savior. The vision of Evangelism Explosion International is the following verse, "Therefore go and make disciples of all nations and baptize them in the Name of the Father and of the Son and the Holy Spirit, and teach them to do everything that I have commanded you. Furthermore, know that I will be with you always until the end of time."

Friendship

Like flying an airplane, the two most difficult things flying an airplane are taking off and landing, so in terms of evangelism, the most challenging thing in evangelism is getting started (takeoff). Many evangelists have failed and even been rejected because of mistakes in gospel preaching. How an evangelist can do the right way to deal with this many things. One of them is through friendship. Friendship begins with introductions, which make it possible to learn more deeply about who and how that person's life and spiritual background is. The association will break the gaps that become separators and good bridge relations, which is much needed for preaching the Gospel (Barton, 1993).

Gospel

The Bible is derived from the Greek namely Euangelio, translated into English as Gospel, and into Indonesian, namely the '*injil*', which means good news or joyful news (Setiawan, 2019). The news of joy here is different from other news of joy that humans also often receive; the news of joy here is related to human salvation because in Romans 3:23, "all have sinned and fall short of the glory of God ". In this verse, it is explained that all humans have sinned and have been separated and have even lost the image and likeness of God, which causes humans to live apart from God; as a result, "the wages of sin is death but the grace of God is eternal life in His son Jesus Christ" (Rom 6:23).

Humans who have sinned must be angered and destroyed in death because their lives are no longer acceptable to God. All mankind must die and perish because the wages of sin are death. However, death is not God's intention for humans because God loves humans so much. Humans are so precious in front of God that because of His great love, God plans a plan to save humans until, in John 3:16, it is said, "Because God's

love for this world is so great that He gave His only Son so that everyone who believes in Him will not perish but have eternal life". That is the news of joy or the Gospel, where the second person of the Triune God, the creator of the universe, has taken form in mortal flesh to become a human being." In the beginning is the word; and the word was with God, and the Word was God.....the word became man and dwelt among us".

Surrender

Surrender or statement of commitment requires caution, like landing an airplane. Not being careful with proper calculations can fail the mission of the Gospel. James Kennedy said that "Commitment is the "hinge" part of the presentation, refocusing from understanding Calvin about the Bible Coconut, what do you want him to do. Everything that was done before the commitment was directed at the action of this commitment, and everything that follows is determined based on the candidate's response to that commitment" (Wonatorei & Waani, 2021).

James Kennedy said, "Many witnesses or evangelists are afraid to ask for a commitment because they are not well prepared, or they don't know whether they have succeeded in getting the candidate to understand the Bible, or they are rejected." One necessary thing is that before making a question about commitment, candidate must first candidate what a commitment is and what it is necessary to commit. Reason to express commitments candidate must first understand the contents of the news so that he wants to declare his faith as a pledge before God and as a witness; we are not too afraid because the work to make people repent is the work of the Holy Spirit (Surya &Setiawati, 2020).

Follow-up

Like a newborn child, a person who has just received treatment needs a lot of attention and guidance from more spiritually mature people. Because it would be hazardous for new converts to walk alone because there will be so many heretical teachings that can damage their faith. Therefore, follow-up is needed or often referred to as follow-up. We have to take responsibility as spiritual parents to continue to foster and develop the spiritual child's faith (Benjamin & Gratia, 2020).

James Kennedy said, "Your responsibility as spiritual parents is not finished until you do everything possible to develop your students into members of the local church that can produce new disciples" (Kause, 2021).

The church is an eternal family of God, where its members consist of old and young, adults and young adults. In the church, immature local people are nurtured because, in the church, the new believer finds the environment he needs to continue to grow and serve God.

RESEARCH METHODS

This research is an exploratory-confirmatory survey. Survey research is research used in large and small populations. However, the data used is data from samples as representatives of the population to find events that relate, distribution and the relationships between the variables studied, using a questionnaire (Fred & Howard, 2000). It is called a survey because it uses a representative population sample. Meanwhile, confirmatory research is research conducted to test explanatory results (Mitra Prajna Andal, 2020)

The population in this study were everyone who had attended Evangelism Explosion training and people who had been served using the Evangelism Explosion method at GPII in the North Sumatra Region. At the same time, the samples taken were 100 people from all EEI training participants. At the same time, the data collection tool used is a questionnaire that is measured using a Likert scale and has been tested for validity and reliability. The data analysis technique used is path analysis (Path-Analysis) with the principles of regression.

Figure 1: Research Framework

The design of the relationship pattern between variables is based on the Construct/Theological study/Research Theory

Information:

AND = Mission Implication

X1 = Friendship

x2 = the Bible

X3 = Surrender

X4 = Follow Up

Based on the research framework, the hypothesis formulation is obtained as follows:

- 1) The EE alumni in the Indonesian Evangelical Presbyterian Church in the Northern Sumatra region implement the EE personal evangelism method with a certain (moderate) tendency.
- 2) There is a pattern of correlation (correlation) between variables that describes the EE personal evangelism method implementation among EE alumni in the Indonesian Evangelical Presbyterian Church in the Northern Sumatra region.
- 3) There is a contribution between variables towards implementing the EE personal evangelism method among EE alumni in the Indonesian Evangelical Presbyterian Church in the Northern Sumatra region.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data Description

Table 1: Description of Friendship Variable Data

Statistics		
Persahabatan		
N	Valid	100
	Missing	0
Mean		42,2500
Median		42,0000
Mode		47,00
Std. Deviation		4,16667
Variance		17,361
Skewness		-,682
Std. Error of Skewness		,241
Kurtosis		,275
Std. Error of Kurtosis		,478
		19,00
Minimum		30,00
Maximum		49,00

On the Friendship variable, the Mean is 42.25. Median 42. Mode 47. Standard Deviation 4.16667. Variance 17.361. Skewness -0.682. Kurtosis 0.275. Range 19. Minimum 30. Maximum 49.

Test Requirements Analysis

Normality test

The data normality test was conducted to see whether the research data were normally distributed (Sintia et al., 2022). The method used is to observe the points found on the following Normal P-P Plot graphics:

Normal P-P Plot of Regression Standardized Residual

Figure 2: P-Plot Graph

On the graph, the dots follow a diagonal line. Thus, the research data is usually distributed.

Multicollinearity Test

The assumptions of path analysis follow the general assumptions of linear regression, namely that multicollinearity symptoms should not occur between independent variables. The method is to observe score VIF (Variance Inflation Factor) (Lolowang et al., 2016). The condition for the data that multicollinearity does not occur is VIF-count < 10. This is the calculation:

Table 2: table VIF-Test Multicollinearity

Model		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
1	Persahabatan	,615	1,626
	Injil	,507	1,974
	Penyerahan Diri	,776	1,289
	Tindak Lanjut	,836	1,196

a. Dependent Variable: Implementasi

The table above shows that the VIF values for each exogenous variable are 1.626, 1.974, 1.289 and 1.196. All of them are smaller than 10. Thus, there are no symptoms of multicollinearity between exogenous variables.

First Hypothesis Test: Implementation of Personal Evangelism Methods

Trends in implementing the method evangelism Personal Evangelism Explosion Internationally, it is observed through the Lower and Upper Bound values at the Interval for Mean accepted at a 95% confidence level. Thus the calculation:

Table 3: Table of Intervals for Means

Descriptives			Statistic	Std. Error
Implementasi	Mean		169,8900	1,28895
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	167,3324	
		Upper Bound	172,4476	
	5% Trimmed Mean		170,2667	
	Median		170,0000	
	Variance		166,139	
	Std. Deviation		12,88950	
	Minimum		136,00	
	Maximum		191,00	
	Range		55,00	
	Interquartile Range		21,50	
	Skewness		-,215	,241
	Kurtosis		-,521	,478

The first step is determining Class (k) of 5, with the categories Very Low, Low, Medium, High and Very High. Next, determine the Interval class (i) obtained from Range/Class = 55/5 = 11, rounded to 12.

Table 4: Categories of Method Implementation

Class	Category	Description
136 – 147	Very low	Score Lower-Upper Bound 167,3324 – 172,4476
148 – 159	Low	
160 – 171	medium	
172 – 183	high	Masuk pada kategori Sedang, menuju ke Tinggi
184 – 195	Very high	

The table above shows that the Lower and Upper Bound values are located in the Moderate category, leading to the High category. That is, the level of implementation of the Evangelism Personal Evangelism Method Explosion International at the Indonesian Evangelical Presbyterian Church in the North Sumatra Region is mediocre or mediocre. However, there are indications to move higher.

Second Hypothesis Test: Analysis of Relationships between Variables

The second hypothesis test was conducted to analyze how big the relationship pattern of Friendship, Gospel, Surrender and Follow-up. The test is carried out by observing the Pearson correlation coefficient, arranged into a correlation matrix.

Correlation Matrix

The correlation matrix between variables is arranged based on the following SPSS processing table:

Table 5: Correlation between Variables

		Correlations			
		Persaha batan	Injil	Penyerah an Diri	Tindak Lanjut
Persahabatan	Pearson Correlation	1	,597**	,393**	,138
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.	,000	,000	,170
	N	100	100	100	100
Injil	Pearson Correlation	,597**	1	,442**	,385**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,000	.	,000	,000
	N	100	100	100	100
Penyerahan Diri	Pearson Correlation	,393**	,442**	1	,104
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,000	,000	.	,303
	N	100	100	100	100
Tindak Lanjut	Pearson Correlation	,138	,385**	,104	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,170	,000	,303	.
	N	100	100	100	100

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

From the results of the SPSS output above, a correlation matrix between variables can be compiled as follows:

Table 6: Correlation Matrix Between

	Friendship	Gospel	Surrender	Follow-up
Friendship	1,000	0,597	0,393	0,138
Gospel	0,597	1,000	0,442	0,385
Surrender	0,393	0,442	1,000	0,104
Follow-up	0,138	0,385	0,104	1,000

The Friendship indicator has a close relationship with the Gospel indicator (r 0.597, $\text{Sig.}000 < \alpha$ 0.05) and Surrender (r 0.393, $\text{Sig.}000 < \alpha$ 0.05). However, not related to the Follow-up indicator (r 0.138, $\text{Sig.}0.170 > \alpha$ 0.05). The Gospel indicator is closely

related to the Surrender indicator ($r = 0.442$, $\text{Sig.}000 < \alpha 0.05$) and the Follow-up indicator ($r = 0.385$, $\text{Sig.}000 < \alpha 0.05$). Meanwhile, the surrender indicator is unrelated to the follow-up indicator ($r = 0.104$, $\text{Sig.}0.303 > \alpha 0.05$).

Third Hypothesis Test: Contribution of Variables-variable Against the Implementation of Evangelism Personal Evangelism Methods Explosion

The third hypothesis test was conducted to analyze how much Friendship, Gospel, Surrender and Follow-up contributed to the implementation of EE's evangelism method. The test is done by observing the path coefficient (Standardized Coefficient-Beta), arranged into a path coefficient matrix.

Path Coefficient Matrix

The path analysis matrix is determined based on the principle of linear regression. The following is the result of processing with SPSS for each variable:

Table 7: Coefficient of Each Path

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	70,536	8,619		8,184	,000
	Persahabatan	2,352	,203	,760	11,582	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Implementasi

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	72,788	4,468		16,292	,000
	Injil	1,787	,082	,911	21,891	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Implementasi

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	38,311	16,619		2,305	,023
	Penyerahan Diri	2,543	,321	,625	7,932	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Implementasi

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	126,133	7,245		17,410	,000
	Tindak Lanjut	2,030	,332	,525	6,111	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Implementasi

Through the regression processing tables above, a path coefficient matrix can be compiled based on the Beta coefficient value (Standardized Coefficients-Beta) or also known as Beta-count, as follows:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \rho_{YX1} \\ \rho_{YX2} \\ \rho_{YX3} \\ \rho_{YX4} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0,760 \\ 0,911 \\ 0,625 \\ 0,525 \end{pmatrix}$$

Figure 3: Path coefficient matrix

The Friendship Indicator contributed 0.760 units in implementing EEI personal evangelism at GPII in the Sumgut region. While the indicators of the Bible contributed 0.911 units, the Surrender indicator contributed 0.625 units, and the Follow Up indicator contributed 0.525.

Relationship Patterns and Influence of Variables in the Implementation of Evangelism Personal Evangelism Methods Explosion

The numbers in the correlation matrix and path coefficient matrix that have been compiled based on research data processing in the second and third hypothesis tests, if included in the relationship pattern diagram between variables, will appear as follows:

Figure 4: Method Implementation Relationship Pattern

The diagram above can be interpreted this way:

- 1) The Friendship indicator has a close relationship with the Gospel indicator ($r 0.597, \text{Sig}.000 < \alpha 0.05$) and Surrender ($r 0.393, \text{Sig}.000 < \alpha 0.05$). However, it is not related to the Follow-Up indicator ($r 0.138, \text{Sig}.0.170 > \alpha 0.05$), shown through the dotted line. The Gospel indicator is closely related to the Surrender indicator ($r 0.442, \text{Sig}.000 < \alpha 0.05$) and the Follow-up indicator ($r 0.385, \text{Sig}. 000 < \alpha 0.05$). While the surrender indicator is not related to the follow-up indicator ($r 0.104, \text{Sig}. 0.303 > \alpha 0.05$) is shown through the dotted line.

- 2) The Friendship Indicator contributed 0.760 units to implement EEI personal evangelism at GPII in the Sumgut region. While the indicators of the Bible contributed 0.911 units, the Surrender indicator contributed 0.625 units, and the Follow Up indicator contributed 0.525.
- 3) the most significant contribution to the implementation of the EEI personal evangelism method at the GPII in the North Sumatra region is the gospel indicator, which is indicated by a path coefficient of 0.911. Followed by indicators of Friendship, the Gospel of Surrender and Follow Up.

CONCLUSION

From the results of research data processing, it can be concluded several things as follows:

- 1) Level of implementation of Evangelism Personal Evangelism Method Explosion International at the Indonesian Evangelical Presbyterian Church in the Northern Sumatra Region is mediocre. However, there are indications to move higher.
- 2) The Friendship indicator is closely related to the Gospel indicator and the Surrender indicator. However, it is not related to the Follow Up indicator. The Gospel indicator is closely related to the Surrender and Follow-Up indicators. Meanwhile, the surrender indicator is not related to the follow-up indicator.
- 3) The Friendship Indicator contributed 0.760 units to implement EEI personal evangelism at GPII in the Sumgut region. While the indicators of the Bible contribute 0.911 units, the Surrender indicator contributed 0.625 units, and the Follow Up indicator contributed 0.525 units.
- 4) The most significant contribution to the implementation of the EEI personal evangelism method at the GPII in the North Sumatra region is the gospel indicator, which is indicated by a path coefficient of 0.911. Followed by indicators of Friendship, Surrender and Follow Up.

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